

Development of a hierarchical scale to assess the change in physical function of stroke patients in geriatric day hospitals

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A 4-point hierarchical scale to assess the physical function of stroke patients

- **DOMAINS OF ACTIVITIES**
 - self-care
 - household
 - mobility
- **ABILITY**
 - dependent (0)
 - assistance (1)
 - supervision (2)
 - independent (3)

Self-care ability

- **Combing/ shaving**
- **Drinking**
- **Eating**
- **Washing face**
- **Oral cleaning**
- **Undressing Upper**
- **Dressing Upper**
- **Undressing Lower**
- **Dressing Lower**
- **Toileting**
- **Bathing: wash**
- **Bathing: dry**
- **Preparing water**

Household activity

- **Washing smalls**
- **Light cleaning**
- **Hang out washing**
- **Preparing meal**
- **Shopping**
- **Heavy cleaning**

Mobility

- **Sit to stand**
- **Stand to sit**
- **Bed to chair**
- **Indoor (5m)**
- **Up stair (8 steps)**
- **Down stair (8 steps)**
- **Outdoor (50m)**
- **Public transport**

Geriatric day hospital physical functional assessment form

Name: AB Chan

Sex/Age: M/66; OPD No.: GDH921001

Date of adm.: 2/2/1992

Home: alone/ carers/ institution

Diagnosis: Stroke right hemiparesis (onset date: 1/1/1992)

ACTIVITY	ABILITY				DATE/ TOTAL SCORE		
	D	A	S	I	2/2/92	4/4/92	
A. Self-care	0	1	2	3	29	39	
A1 Combing/shaving	.	.	.	*.°			
A2 Drinking	.	.	.	*.°			
A3 Eating	.	.	.	*.°			
A4 Washing face	.	.	.	*.°			
A5 Oral cleaning	.	.	.	*.°			
A6 Undressing Upper	.	.	.	*.°			
A7 Dressing Upper	.	.	.	*.°			
A8 Undressing Lower	.	.	*.	.°			
A9 Dressing Lower	.	.	*.	.°			
A10 Toileting	.	*.	.	.°			
A11 Bathing: wash	.	*.	.	.°			
A12 Bathing: dry	.	*.	.	.°			
A13 Preparing water	.	*.	.	.°			
B. Household	0	1	2	3	4	12	
B1 Washing small items	.	.	*.	.°			
B2 Light cleaning	.	.	*.	.°			
B3 Hang out washing	*.	.	.°	.			
B4 Preparing meal	*.	.	.°	.			
B5 Shopping	*.	.°	.	.			
B6 Heavy cleaning	*.	.°	.	.			
C. Mobility	0	1	2	3	16	22	
C1 Sit to stand	.	.	.	*.°			
C2 Stand to sit	.	.	.	*.°			
C3 Bed to chair	.	.	.	*.°			
C4 Indoor (5 m)	.	.	.	*.°			
C5 Up stair (8 steps)	.	*.	.	.°			
C6 Down stair (8 steps)	.	*.	.	.°			
C7 Outdoor (50 m)	.	*.	.°	.			
C8 Public transport	.	*.	.°	.			

Scoring 0 Dependent patient cannot participate;
 ≥2 assistance
 1 Assistance; one manual assistance
 2 Supervision; verbal prompting
 3 Independent; ±aids

Profiles

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Dates
 2/ 2/1992
 4/ 4/1992

Patients and Methods

- **436 stroke patients discharged from two geriatric day hospitals over 18 months**
- **the scale was used to assess the physical function of stroke patients on admission and at discharge**

Results: Patient characteristics

- Mean age 73 years (SD 8.4)
- Female/ male ratio 1.3
- Duration of stay: 38 visits (SD 32)
220 days (SD 289)

Results: Changes in self-care & mobility

		Self-care		Mobility	
		Initial(SD)	Change	Initial(SD)	Change
Overall	(n=436)	28.94(7.42)	+2.41*	13.09(7.83)	+2.97*
GDH1	(n=221)	27.76(7.26)	+3.02*	11.73(7.66)	+3.47*
GDH2	(n=215)	30.15(7.40)	+1.79*	14.50(7.79)	+2.45*

* p < 0.000

Results of subgroup with household function assessed (n=28)

Household		Self-care		Mobility	
Initial(SD)	Change	Initial(SD)	Change	Initial(SD)	Change
11.68(3.49)	+2.00	37.43(2.76)	+1.14	17.04(4.44)	+3.18
[max 18]	[p<0.005]	[max 39]	[p<0.031]	[max 24]	[p<0.000]

Conclusion

- **Scale acceptable to patients/staff**
- **Graphical (2-D)representation in profile format facilitates**
 - **identification of items to focus on**
 - **monitor of progress**
- **Summary scores for self-care, household and mobility are sensitive to change**
- **When self-care score reaches ceiling, household and mobility scores remain sensitive**